

**A STUDY ON TEACHERS' MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGY AND
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY
STUDENTS**

A. S. Arul Lawrence,
*Research Supervisor,
School of Education,
Tamil Nadu Open University,
Chennai, India.*

T. Hanitha,
*M.Phil. Scholar,
School of Education,
Tamil Nadu Open University,
Chennai, India*

Abstract

The investigators made an attempt to find out the influence of teachers' motivational strategies and academic achievement of higher secondary students. The sample for the present study consisted of 600 higher secondary school students studying in Kancheepuram educational district. The investigators used simple random sampling technique to collect the data. For collecting data the investigators used self-made Teachers' Motivational Strategy Scale and used the marks obtained by the students in the quarterly examinations as Academic Achievement. For analyzing and interpreting data, the investigator has used percentage analysis, standard deviation, mean, t-test and correlation analysis as statistical techniques. The finding shows that there is a significant positive relationship between teacher's motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Keywords: *Teachers' Motivational Strategy, Academic Achievement, Higher Secondary Student, Motivation, Teaching Strategy*

Introduction

Teachers are key actors who shape the learning environment and whose main tasks include motivating students to learn. Teachers can differ in the way in which they try to motivate students to learn and their motivational strategies can vary from person to person (Hornstra, et al., 2015). According to Dweck (1986) a teacher has only to develop goals that focus on mastery rather than on performance of a task.

Students need to internalize that it is more important to focus on if and how they learned and not on whether they did better than their classmates. Consequently, the focus shifts from a performance goal to a mastery goal. Teachers, therefore need to develop goals orientated toward developing students' abilities and not toward adequacy of their abilities. So, the teachers' motivational strategies in the classroom are very essential to achieve the students' academic achievement.

Significant of the study

In all educational institutions, the whole teaching-learning process is directed towards achievement in the academic field as well as in the sphere of co-curricular activities. The academic achievement is required to be of greater value and for the attainment of which the students, teachers and parents strive towards it (Verma, 2016). Achievement is the act of accomplishing attaining or finishing something that has been accomplished successfully, especially by means of skill, practice or preference. The innate phenomenon, motivation is influenced by environmental factors. In order to achieve their goals, needs and instincts, human beings acquire sufficient motivation. Particularly with respect to students, motivation for academic achievement is of great importance. By such motivation people are stimulated to successfully complete an assignment, achieving a goal or a degree of qualification in their profession. In educational perspective, motivation has a multi-dimensional structure which is correlated with learning and academic motivation (Mohamadi, 2006). So the investigator wants to study about the various teachers' motivational strategy and how it influences the students' achievement in different aspects.

Title of the Study

The present study is entitled as "A study on Teachers' Motivational Strategy and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students".

Operational Definition of the Key Terms

- **Teachers Motivational Strategy:** Teachers are using different motivational strategy and various techniques in the classroom. It includes the following dimensions; achievement, incentive, fear, power and social.

- **Academic Achievement** refers to how the student performs in the examination and how much marks secured from the examination. The total marks earned by the students are considered as academic achievement of student.
- **Higher Secondary Students** refers to those who are studying XI and XII standard in higher secondary schools from Kancheepuram Educational District.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out whether there is any significant difference between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students in their academic achievement.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their academic achievement.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their academic achievement.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between teacher's motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.
- There is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.
- There is no significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.
- There is no significant difference between joint and nuclear family higher

secondary students in their academic achievement.

- There is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their academic achievement.
- There is no significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their academic achievement.
- There is no significant relationship between teachers' motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Methods and Procedures

The investigators used survey method to find out the relationship between teacher motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students. The sample for the present study consisted of 600 higher secondary school students studying in Kancheepuram educational district. The investigators used simple random sampling technique to collect the data. For collecting data the investigators used self-made Teachers' Motivational Strategy Scale and used the marks obtained by the students in the quarterly examinations as Academic Achievement. For analyzing and interpreting data, the investigator has used percentage analysis, standard deviation, mean, t-test and correlation analysis as statistical techniques.

Data Analysis

H_01 : There is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.

Table-1: Difference between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy

Teachers Motivational Strategy	Type of family	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
Achievement	Joint	390	47.73	8.80	0.05	NS
	Nuclear	210	47.68	9.38		
Incentive	Joint	390	50.24	8.85	0.83	NS
	Nuclear	210	49.60	9.02		

Fear	Joint	390	38.61	10.73	0.28	NS
	Nuclear	210	38.87	10.52		
Power	Joint	390	36.49	8.29	0.01	NS
	Nuclear	210	36.50	8.42		
Social	Joint	390	37.09	11.61	0.18	NS
	Nuclear	210	36.90	11.94		
Teachers Motivational Strategy	Joint	390	210.16	23.70	0.28	NS
	Nuclear	210	209.56	24.88		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96, S- Significant, NS- Non Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.

Table-2: Difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy

Teachers Motivational Strategy	Sources of variation	df = 2,597		Calculate d 'F' value	Remarks at 5% level
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Achievement	Between	5263.73	2631.86	36.25	S
	Within	43335.80	72.58		
Incentive	Between	1373.83	686.91	8.87	S
	Within	46203.03	77.39		
Fear	Between	3049.38	1524.69	14.00	S
	Within	64973.81	108.83		
Power	Between	8423.24	4211.62	75.78	S
	Within	33178.74	55.57		
Social	Between	19443.17	9721.58	92.36	S
	Within	62838.49	105.25		

Teachers Motivational Strategy	Between	31785.37	15892.6 8	29.99	S
	Within	316316.9 1	529.84		

(At 5% level of significance, for (2,597) df the table value of 'F' is 3.02)

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their achievement, incentive, fear, power, social and teachers' motivational strategy.

H_03 : There is no significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy.

Table-3: Difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy

Teachers Motivational Strategy	Sources of variation	df = 2,597		Calculate d 'F' value	Remarks at 5% level
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Achievement	Between	590.93	295.46	3.67	S
	Within	48008.60	80.41		
Incentive	Between	54.39	27.19	0.34	NS
	Within	47522.46	79.60		
Fear	Between	1788.67	894.33	8.06	S
	Within	66234.51	110.94		
Power	Between	2797.32	1398.66	21.51	S
	Within	38804.66	64.99		
Social	Between	8076.49	4038.24	32.48	S
	Within	74205.17	124.29		
Teachers Motivational Strategy	Between	20716.99	10358.4 9	18.88	S
	Within	327385.3 0	548.38		

(At 5% level of significance, for (2,597) df the table value of 'F' is 3.02)

It is inferred from the above table there is no significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their incentive. But there is significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their achievement, fear, power, social and teachers motivational strategy.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference between joint and nuclear family higher secondary students in their academic achievement.

Table-4: Difference between joint and nuclear family higher secondary students in their academic achievement

Variable	Type of family	N	Mean	S.D	Calculate d 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
Academic achievement	joint	390	49.64	11.44	2.62	S
	nuclear	210	47.64	7.183		

(At 5% level of significance the table value of 't' is 1.96, S- Significant, NS- Non Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference between joint and nuclear family higher secondary students in their academic achievement.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their academic achievement.

Table-5: Difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their academic achievement

Variable	Sources of variation	df = 2,597		Calculate d 'F' value	Remarks at 5% level
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Academic achievement	Between	844.01	422.00	4.10	S
	Within	61391.57	102.83		

(At 5% level of significance, for (2,597) df the table value of 'F' is 3.02)

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their academic achievement.

H_06 : There is no significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their academic achievement.

Table-6: Difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their academic achievement

Variable	Sources of variation	df = 2,597		Calculate d 'F' value	Remarks at 5% level
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Academic achievement	Between	2494.22	1247.11	12.46	S
	Within	59741.37	100.06		

It is inferred from the above table there is significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their academic achievement.

H_07 : There is no significant relationship between teacher's motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Table-7: Relationship between teacher's motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students

Variable	N	df	Calculated 'γ' value	Table value at 5% level	Remarks
Teachers Motivational Strategy Vs. Academic Achievement	600	598	0.232	0.088	S

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant relationship between teacher's motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Discussion and Conclusion

No significant difference was found between nuclear and joint family higher secondary students. Significant difference was found among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their achievement, incentive, fear,

power, social and teachers' motivational strategy. While comparing the mean scores of boys, girls and co-education schools, the co-education school students are better than boys and girls schools students in their achievement, incentive. But the girls and co-educational school students are better than boys' schools students in their fear, power, social and teachers' motivational strategy in total. Significant difference was found among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their teachers' motivational strategy except the dimension incentive. While comparing the mean scores of government, aided and unaided school higher secondary students in the dimension of achievement, fear, power, social and teachers' motivational strategy, the aided and government school students are better than unaided school students in their achievement. The unaided and aided school students are better than government school students in their fear, power, social and teachers' motivational strategy.

In the case of academic achievement, significant difference was found between joint and nuclear family higher secondary students in their academic achievement. There was significant difference among boys, girls and co-education school higher secondary students in their academic achievement. While comparing the mean scores of girls, boys and co-education schools, the boys and co-education school students are better than girls' school students in their academic achievement. There was significant difference among government, aided and unaided schools higher secondary students in their academic achievement. While comparing the mean scores of government, aided and unaided school higher secondary students in their academic achievement, the government school students are better than unaided and aided school students. A strong positive correlation was found between teacher's motivational strategy and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

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